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THE IMPORTANCE OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN PEDAGOGY.

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Abstract: In this article, ideas are presented about ways to improve the lives of children with developmental disabilities, help them find their place in society, and the role of education in this.

Key words: inclusive education, competence, knowledge, skills, competence, evaluation methods, health promotion, society.

In any society, it is hoped that the young generation will grow up as mature and perfect people in all respects, grow up as worthy citizens and contribute to the development and prosperity of the state. According to the Convention on the Rights of the Child, which belongs to all children of the world, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", as well as a number of important regulatory documents, all children, including physical and mental development Children with disabilities also have the right to work, get education, and find their place in life. In recent years, the concept of inclusive education is often mentioned, many people understand this concept only as the fact that children with disabilities study in the same school, in the same class, and sit at the same desk as healthy children. "Actually, it's not only that. Inclusive education means that all children are educated in the same school and in the same classroom under the same conditions. That is, a child with disabilities should be able to study with the same attention as healthy children. "A child of a low-income family should not go to an unrenovated school just because he is from a poor family," says Oybek Isakov, chairman of the Disabled People's Association of Uzbekistan. In Uzbekistan, regardless of family circumstances, all children attend state comprehensive schools. It is guaranteed by the state. Only those who want to can study in private schools paying their own money. However, it is impossible to brag about the fact that children with disabilities study in equal conditions with other healthy children. There are many problems in this regard. The main problems in this regard were listed in the presidential decision "On measures to further improve the system of education for children with special educational needs" adopted on October 13, 2020. The issue of gradual

introduction of inclusive general education until 2025 was raised by the President's decision. Tasks such as creating a barrier-free environment for children with disabilities to come to schools, building newly built schools with similar conditions, training pedagogic personnel, and improving the educational base have been defined. However, it is advisable to start this educational system from the child's preschool age. Inclusive education is derived from the English language and means inclusive, inclusion. This education is aimed at eliminating barriers (discrimination) between disabled and able-bodied children, children in need of special education, children (disabled for some reasons) regardless of developmental defects or economic difficulties. Inclusive education is an educational system that represents inclusion in the general education process aimed at adapting to social life.

Today's new image of Uzbekistan is in harmony with positive changes in the field of education. A number of reforms are being carried out in the education of children with disabilities, as in any field, based on the advanced trends of the world. In addition to healthy children, legal standards have been developed in order to organize the education of children with special needs in accordance with the child's unique and hidden capabilities. In our country, the legal framework for the protection of children's rights has been created, a number of laws have been adopted, and children's rights have been guaranteed in them. In 1992, the Republic of Uzbekistan ratified the Convention on the Rights of the Child (adopted by the UN on November 20, 1989). This Convention is the most universal child protection document of the UN. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Children's Rights" provides for the provision of the rights, freedoms and legal interests of the child, protection of life and health, prevention of discrimination, honor and dignity of the child. protection of its value and implementation of other socially and politically important tasks are guaranteed. In addition, during the last 5 years, the issue of reforming education, providing employment for citizens, and ensuring comfortable living conditions has been raised to the level of state policy.

The fourth direction of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the development of the social sphere, the tasks defined in it indicate that the priority of humanitarian ideas in our country and the important value of kindness characteristic of our nation¹. In particular, tasks such as strengthening the social protection of the needy segments of the population, state support for the elderly and persons with disabilities, and improving the provision of social services to them require the radical improvement of the education system of children with

disabilities and the introduction of innovative technologies into this process. The educational process of children with disabilities is derived from the laws of the educational process of healthy children and also has its own characteristics. Deaf and hard-of-hearing, blind, and mentally retarded children, as well as healthy children, go through each of the stages of human development. The norm contains age-specific limits of development and certain standard sizes. Such development includes both physical and mental development of the child in accordance with his age. However, each child has its own unrepeatable characteristics. These characteristics are related to the physiological and psychological development of children. The principle of activity envisages planning and carrying out development work, understanding the age at which the child is passing and what activity is a priority for him during this period. Purposeful organization of education not only in educational institutions, but also in families is one of the important conditions for raising children to become spiritually mature, physically strong, intellectually competitive specialists. In conclusion, it can be said that disabled children live in a negative emotional environment and have negative behavior. Comprehensive preparation work is required in the entire community where the child lives, because any child, especially a disabled child, has a social behavior depends on the social environment in which he lives.

Implementation of integration or inclusive education in pre-school educational organizations without providing correctional and pedagogical support to children with disabilities, communicating with families, providing them with special educational literature, and creating special conditions for them will not bring positive results. . This approach is a type of physical integration.

In order to solve the above problems, it is necessary to find a solution to the following issues: - In order to harmonize the education of children with disabilities, it is necessary to identify them from an early age, diagnose them, send them to appropriate organizations for education, and develop alternative types of continuous special education. Creating conditions for the education of children with mental and physical disabilities, determining the content of education for children raised at home based on their capabilities and needs, developing individual programs, inclusive education for parents and teachers The development of educational and methodical literature in the field of education, the involvement of modern pedagogical and information technologies

in education, the organization of distance education through Internet networks is a task facing our society and experts.

- Organization of non-state, non-profit preschool educational organizations that educate children with special needs due to the low level of coverage of children with special needs.

- Organization of rehabilitation (health) pre-school educational organizations based on the regional level.

Another advantage of the introduction of inclusive education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is that it creates an opportunity for children with disabilities to be involved in the system of preschool education organizations even in areas where there are no special education organizations.

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